

Could Octopus help researchers
produce high quality, open
research?

Interviews and focus groups

This report has been published with the digital object identifier (DOI): [10.5281/zenodo.10407225](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10407225)

Authors and contributions

Author contributions are based on the [CRediT](#) contributor roles taxonomy.

Pen-Yuan Hsing ([ORCID](#) 0000-0002-5394-879X) - conceptualisation (equal); investigation (lead); formal analysis (lead); data curation (equal); methodology (equal); project administration (equal); validation (lead); writing – original draft (lead); writing – review and editing (equal).

Alex Freeman ([ORCID](#) 0000-0002-4115-161X) - conceptualisation (lead); funding acquisition (lead); methodology (equal); project administration (supporting); supervision (supporting); writing – review and editing (equal).

Marcus Munafò ([ORCID](#) 0000-0002-4049-993X) - conceptualisation (supporting); funding acquisition (lead); supervision (lead).

Jackie Thompson ([ORCID](#) 0000-0003-2851-3636) - conceptualisation (equal); methodology (supporting); project administration (supporting); supervision (supporting); writing – review and editing (equal).

License

© 2023 The authors.

This document, unless otherwise noted for specific components, is shared under the [Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International](#) (CC BY-SA 4.0) license.

This means you have the freedoms to:

- **Share** — copy and redistribute this material in any medium or format.
- **Adapt** — remix, transform, and build upon this material for any purpose, even commercially.

As long as you meet the following conditions:

- **Attribution** — You must give [appropriate credit](#), provide a link to this license, and [indicate if changes were made](#). You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests endorsement by the original authors (licensor) of you or your use.
- **ShareAlike** — If you remix, transform, or build upon this material, you must distribute your contributions under the [same license](#) as the original (i.e. CC BY-SA 4.0).
- **No additional restrictions** — You may not apply legal terms or [technological measures](#) that legally restrict others from doing anything this license permits.

Table of contents

Executive summary	1
Summary of findings.....	2
Methods	3
Focus groups.....	4
Interviews.....	6
Results	10
Focus groups.....	10
Interviews.....	11
Analysis	12
Feedback on Octopus features.....	12
How is Octopus already useful?.....	14
Barriers to adopting Octopus.....	15
Interpretation	22
Insights into research culture.....	22
Perceptions of Octopus.....	22
Real World Application	24
Communicating Octopus.....	24
Technical changes.....	25
User experience.....	26
Organisational strategies.....	27
Policy implications.....	28
Appendix	29
Positionality statements.....	29
Acknowledgements.....	29
References	31

Executive Summary

Octopus (<https://www.octopus.ac/>) is a new research publishing platform with the goal of reforming how research is conducted, shared, and reviewed. It is different from other open research platforms by breaking down the reporting of research into eight distinct elements:

- Research problem
- Rationale/hypothesis
- Methods
- Results
- Analysis
- Interpretation
- Real world application
- Peer review of any of the above

This platform encourages the publication of research in smaller, granular increments, with a lower barrier to entry compared to the traditional journal article format. In addition to being free-of-charge for authors, Octopus is distinct from other platforms because it requires published items to be linked to one another. For example, a method proposed by one researcher could be linked to a hypothesis (or multiple hypotheses) published by another.

Ultimately, Octopus aims to reform research culture in five ways:

1. Reducing barriers and hierarchies that restrict research sharing, leading to more meritocratic recognition (especially for early career researchers and specialists)
2. Reducing pressures that can lead to questionable research practices (QRPs)
3. Addressing factors that lead to certain topics and types of research being favoured
4. Reducing bias in the assessment of publications and their quality
5. Encouraging more openly collaborative ways of thinking and working – division of labour and open critique of all parts of the research process

To understand how Octopus may fit into existing research culture, [we previously conducted](#) a baseline evaluation of the academic research and publishing ecosystem (Hsing et al. 2023a).

The current study builds on that evaluation by understanding how Octopus is received by stakeholders, and how the platform could be improved to better achieve its aims. To do so, we conducted the following:

- **Focus groups** - We invited researchers across disciplines (humanities, sciences, and engineering) to 1-hour focus groups. These comprised open-ended guiding questions regarding their initial reaction to the Octopus platform and how it works, and the facilitators and barriers to using Octopus in their day-to-day research.

- **Semi-structured interviews** - We conducted a series of semi-structured, 1-hour interviews with those managing research infrastructure, broadly defined. This may be those who work in libraries, research funding bodies, or supporting researcher development. These interviews are to elucidate how Octopus may or may not fit into existing research practices on the institutional level.

What is open research?

For the purposes of this report, we refer to open research as the set of practices which produce open knowledge [as defined by the Open Knowledge Foundation](#):

“Knowledge is open if anyone [has the freedoms] to access, use, modify, and share it — subject, at most, to measures that preserve provenance and openness.”

We also recognise that open research should include considerations such as, but not limited to, if and how to make sensitive data available as guided by the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable ([FAIR](#)) principles for data.

Summary of findings

Interviewees and focus group participants generally perceived Octopus to be a positive step towards the more open sharing of research outputs. In particular, some appreciated the granular recognition of research labour that Octopus publications enable. However, similar to the findings from our previous evaluation, most researchers do not believe they will actively publish on Octopus. This is because of the perception that doing so will not benefit, or even be detrimental, to career advancement as traditional peer-reviewed papers are what counts. Some also expressed a fear of scooping, or that Octopus will not fit into their existing workflows.

Despite these barriers, participant input revealed improvements that could be made to Octopus, and how the platform could coordinate with other organisations to promote more open research. For example, communications about Octopus can more clearly communicate its key differentiators from similar platforms; interoperability could enable programmatic access by researchers and publishers to automate tasks; partnering with traditional publishers to act as the official repository for supplementary materials; or engagement with non-STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) fields of research.

The rest of this report discusses in more detail our methodology, findings, analysis, and their actionable implications for improving Octopus. The sections are organised in the style of, and published as, Methods, Results, Analysis, Interpretation, and Real World Application publications on Octopus.

Methods

Through a [survey](#) (Hsing et al. 2023b) and [interviews](#) (Hsing et al. 2023c), we previously conducted a baseline evaluation of research culture across different disciplines, including obtaining researchers' views on what may motivate or hinder sharing research more openly.

In this second stage, we continue the evaluation, but focus on feedback about the Octopus platform itself. To obtain this feedback, we asked the following of interview and focus group participants:

1. **How is the Octopus user interface/user experience (UI/UX) received by researchers?** Specifically:
 - a. How effectively is the website communicating the goals of Octopus to different types of researchers, and how it works?
 - b. How discoverable, understandable, and usable are the features of Octopus? What are the facilitators and barriers to their use?
2. **How well does Octopus fit into existing research culture and infrastructure?** We would like the perspectives of:
 - a. Individual researchers
 - b. Institutional research infrastructure managers

Similar to the previous evaluation, we have a diverse and international network of professional contacts, and participant recruitment could begin with a snowball approach from a convenient sample from this network. In addition, we can recruit participants through professional organisations. Other potential ways to reach participants include:

- Early-career or postdoctoral researcher networks
- Professional societies in various disciplines
- Contacts of Octopus within universities (mainly in Europe, including the United Kingdom)
- Contacts in private companies
- National laboratories/research institutions in the United Kingdom and United States.

We anticipate that, time-wise, participant recruitment and scheduling the focus groups and interviews (described below) will be the least predictable step. Each participant will be offered an incentive worth GBP 25 in the form of an online shopping voucher or donation to a non-profit organisation.

The methods described here have received ethical approval from the University of Bristol School of Psychological Science Research Ethics Committee with reference number 12335.

Focus groups

The methodology of this evaluation is primarily a focus group with researchers, focused on the user experience of Octopus. Participants would be emailed a link to Octopus before the session, and shown a brief demonstration at the beginning of the focus group.

Then, the focus group would commence with some guiding questions on if and how Octopus would fit into a researcher's workflow, and how they perceive the wider culture will respond to this platform. These open-ended questions will provide insight into what may facilitate or hinder the adoption of Octopus.

We intend to run at least two focus groups with five participants each for a total of at least 10 researchers. Online focus groups will be conducted using the Zoom video conferencing tool. Ideally, at least one of the focus groups would be in-person, which may be more conducive to a stimulating discussion among the participants. For the in-person focus group, it will likely be with researchers at the University of Bristol (where we are physically based) due to logistical constraints.

We aim for focus groups to last approximately 60 minutes, with audio recordings that are transcribed into text for analysis. The recordings will be deleted once the transcripts are complete with personally-identifiable information removed.

Participant recruitment

For individual researchers, we will strive to recruit those who represent diversity across the following characteristics:

- Basic dimensions of diversity such as gender
- Geographical location, including outside of the Global North
- Research discipline
 - Natural sciences
 - Social sciences
 - Engineering
 - Arts and humanities
- Research methods employed
 - Qualitative
 - Quantitative
 - Theoretical
 - Applied (e.g., engineering)
- Sector
 - Academic
 - Industry (ideally not just the pharmaceutical industry)
 - Ideally some from none of the above

- Publish other research objects (i.e. not code or “data”) such as:
 - Multimedia
 - Hardware designs
 - Digitised resources
 - Non-article-based publication types (e.g. monographs, art pieces)

Pre-focus group engagement

Approximately one week before the focus group, we will email and request participants to visit Octopus (<https://www.octopus.ac/>) with guiding questions including: “In these 5 minutes, can you...”:

1. Find and understand the key motivations behind Octopus?
2. Identify the types of research that could be published on Octopus?

Focus group plan (approximately 60 mins)

1. **Quickly introduce yourselves (10 mins)** - In two minutes, tell us about your career stage and the nature of your research, including methods and outputs.
2. **Octopus demonstration** - Where the facilitator goes through the Octopus.ac platform, giving an overview of its motivations and key features (15 mins)
 - This could include using a demo account to publish something in real time.
3. **Barriers/facilitators to using Octopus (15 mins)** - Would you want to use Octopus? What about Octopus would make you want or not want to use it?
4. **Perception of how others might react (10 mins)** - Do you think others in your field would want and will use Octopus to publish research? Why or why not?
5. **Feedback form (5 mins)** - Dedicated time for participants to provide additional feedback by answering these questions in writing (no identifying information will be collected, and participants will be asked to not provide it):
 - Which research discipline(s) do you primarily identify with?
 - On a scale of 1 to 5 (with 5 being highest), how familiar are you with open research practices (broadly defined)?
 - Does the organisation of publications on Octopus fit with the research workflow of your discipline(s)? Please explain.

- What would convince you and others in your discipline(s) to make use of Octopus to publish research earlier and more often?
- Do you have any other critique or feedback for Octopus or today's session?

Interviews

In addition to focus groups, we would like to obtain feedback from institutional research infrastructure managers. An example of such a manager could be those in charge of supporting researchers at the University of Bristol through the use of the [data.bris](https://data.bris.ac.uk/) institutional data-sharing platform (this is an example from our institution, we will not interview this specific individual). We will strive to reach those in equivalent roles at other institutions. Depending on the institution, they could be librarians, research support staff, or heads of research. For these infrastructure managers, because they typically operate on the institution level, we believe their experiences and views would cut across many of the criteria we defined for our focus group participants. To be clear, this means we will not be targeting those maintaining the *technical* infrastructure, such as technicians.

Interview guide

The following is the interview guide we will use:

Introduction (5 mins)	
Question	Prompts
Housekeeping	<p>Welcome participant and thank for their time</p> <p>Check if there are any issues with consent form</p> <p>Sound check (no need to do explicitly)</p> <p>Explain how long interview will take and that they can stop/take a break at any time</p> <p>Establish procedure in case of connectivity issues (i.e. try to rejoin ASAP and resume interview when ready)</p> <p>Any questions?</p>
Ask consent to record	

start recording	
Introduce the aims of the study	<p>To find out more about participant's:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Role in supporting research infrastructure b. Immediate reactions after being introduced to Octopus c. Views on if and how Octopus could be a part of their service offering to researchers in their institutions d. Views on what their counterparts at other institutions might think
Part 1: Participant's role (10 mins)	
To start off with, could you tell me a bit about the nature of your work in supporting researchers?	Try to keep it under 2 minutes - don't let them get carried away!
For the research you support, what kinds of output do they produce?	<p>Methods: Quantitative, qualitative, field, etc.</p> <p>What kinds of output do these forms of research produce?</p>
I'd like to zoom out to your institution, what other ways does it support researchers to share research outputs?	<p>Does it work well or poorly? In what ways?</p> <p>What, if anything, would you change about it?</p>
If there is one thing you can change to help you support researchers in sharing more of their research, what might it be?	To identify key barriers to research sharing.
Part 2: Introduction & reactions to Octopus (15-20 mins)	
Interviewer gives a 10 minute introduction to Octopus via shared screen	<p>It will cover:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Motivations for Octopus ● The 8 publication types on Octopus

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● How they form the “version of record” - everything in full, in one place ● Branching chains of research ● Finer grained attribution for researchers ● Can be used for pre-registration, like pre-printing or post-printing. ● Differences with traditional journal articles: sits alongside - like having all the supplementary information in there. ● If time permits, could share two example publications: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://doi.org/10.57874/gv8n-ap7Z ○ https://doi.org/10.57874/xw90-dm13 <p>Participants can interrupt and ask clarifying questions throughout this introduction. This means that this part might last longer than 10 minutes, and the interviewer will carefully watch the time, leaving enough for the next part.</p>
<p>Part 3: How might Octopus fit into research support infrastructure? (10 mins)</p>	
<p>What do you think of Octopus?</p>	<p>What are your initial reactions?</p>
<p>How might Octopus fit into research support infrastructure?</p>	
<p>What are some barriers that might prevent your institution from including Octopus as part of its offering of support for researchers?</p>	
<p>In contrast, what have you seen today that would help/facilitate your institution to include Octopus in its offering?</p>	

<p>How do you think those providing research support infrastructure at other institutions might think about Octopus?</p>	
<p>Closing (5 mins)</p>	
<p>Is there anything that we haven't discussed that you'd like to talk about before the end of the interview?</p>	
<p>**stop recording**</p>	
	<p>Thank the participant for their time.</p> <p>Explain next steps (debrief, final consent etc)</p> <p>Explain data management procedures (i.e. when will interview recordings be deleted, how will transcripts be anonymised etc)</p> <p>Ask if they would like to be acknowledged</p> <p>Any questions?</p> <p>Contact details for questions/concerns</p>

Results

Focus groups

The recruitment of focus group participants began in June 2023, which coincided with the beginning of academic breaks in most of Europe and North America. This timing made recruitment difficult, as the researchers we contacted often did not reply or were unavailable. For researchers who agreed to participate, scheduling an in-person focus group was also difficult due to travel for breaks. Therefore, all focus groups were conducted online.

Three focus groups were conducted with a total of 11 participants across multiple fields of research between July and August 2023 (**Table 1**), seven of whom were women. With one exception of an assistant professor, participants were early career researchers (e.g., at the postdoctoral level but without a lectureship or professorship position) as we received no responses from researchers in later career stages (e.g., professors). The majority (n = 8) of participants were based at the University of Bristol as we were most successful in eliciting responses within the university.

Table 1. *Self-described research positions and research fields of the 11 focus group participants in our evaluation.*

Research position	Field of research
Assistant professor	History, literature, and philosophy
Independent researcher	Digital humanities and computational social sciences
Staff scientist at research institute	Theoretical physics and systems biology
Staff scientist at research institute	Bioinformatics
Postdoctoral researcher	Biomedicine and virology
Postdoctoral researcher	Biomedicine and microbiology
Postdoctoral researcher	Biomedicine and cell disease
Postdoctoral researcher	Planetary science
Postdoctoral researcher	Quantum physics
Postdoctoral researcher	Aerospace engineering
Postdoctoral research fellow	Abstract and pure mathematics

While we have reached researchers representing a variety of disciplines, from the humanities to science and engineering, the participants were not as diverse across other dimensions such as career stage or geographical location.

Transcripts with personally-identifying information redacted are not currently published.

Interviews

The recruitment of interviewees began in June 2023, which coincided with the beginning of academic breaks in many European and North American research institutions. This timing made recruitment difficult, as the individuals we contacted often did not reply or were unavailable.

Interviews with five participants representing three institutions took place between July and September 2023 (**Table 2**), four of whom were women. Three participants were based at the University of Bristol as we were most successful in eliciting responses from within our university.

Table 2. *Research infrastructure managers interviewed and their roles.*

Role	Institution	Job
Librarian	Research university	Promote data publishing and the use of research metrics, mainly with social sciences and health researchers.
Librarian	Research university	Manage institutional data repository and advise researchers on data management.
Researcher development officer	Research university	Facilitate academic staff development for all faculties - from arts to the sciences.
Open science lead	Non-profit medical research funding body	Develop and promote open science practices within the organisation and the research it funds.
Librarian	National research policy agency (former); PhD student at research university (current)	Develop national-level research policy and infrastructure for a Southeast Asian country.

Transcripts with personally-identifying information redacted are not currently published.

Analysis

Participants had varying levels of familiarity with Octopus prior to the interviews and focus groups. After the Octopus platform was explained during the sessions, participants demonstrated in the ensuing discussion an understanding of key features such as: the motivations for creating Octopus; its eight publication types; how they form the “version of record” while facilitating branching chains of research; finer grained attribution for researchers; and possible use as a form of pre-registration.

Both researchers and research support staff identified ways in which Octopus could already be a useful part of the research lifecycle. However, the majority of their responses focused on cultural and systemic barriers to the widespread adoption of Octopus for research publishing. These issues, and specific feedback on the features of Octopus, are described below.

Feedback on Octopus features

Before being given a verbal explanation of the primary motivations and features of Octopus, it was unclear to several participants how it differs from other open research publishing platforms. One librarian visited the Octopus homepage prior to their interview and asked: “Why would you choose this over something else [such as the Open Science Framework]?” They noted that the primary differentiators of Octopus—such as its eight linked publication types, granular authorship, and branching chains of research—are not obvious at first glance. Another researcher remarked that, upon a cursory inspection, it was unclear if Octopus expects or allows authors to upload their dataset directly to a “Results” publication.

Once the key functionalities and workflows of Octopus have been explained, several researchers questioned whether this platform would be easier to use than those employed by academic journal publishers. According to one biomedical researcher: “...one thing that would make me choose [Octopus] instead of other [sic] is how easy it is to load the things on it... like all of the editing steps that are very often very annoying and different from every platform or every journal”. That is, this researcher may be more willing to publish on Octopus if it is easy to use. As will be discussed below, researchers are time-limited, and they anticipate usage of Octopus will be low “if you’re going to have to spend ages getting everything in the right format”.

In particular, interviewees took note of the branching publication chains enabled by Octopus. Some observed that these branches are akin to “forks” of Git-based (<https://git-scm.com/>) version control code repositories. One librarian has experience supporting national-level research policy and sees these branches as a potentially effective way to facilitate multidisciplinary collaboration, a key goal of their policy. That said, some found it unclear how peer reviews published on Octopus would be visualised as part of a chain, while others were confused whether explicit links to existing items are required when publishing to Octopus.

A common concern was how Octopus implements quality control and moderation of published items, including for spam or other inappropriate content. It was also not clear whether permission from the author is needed before linking to an existing publication. For peer reviews, one asked:

"Can anybody just show up and review? Does that sound a bit weird?" Specifically, one librarian was concerned about whether Octopus publications are tied into automated plagiarism detectors, and ambivalence on whether that will help or hinder publications. This is not just about screening submissions to Octopus. They were especially concerned that if a researcher publishes to Octopus first, their subsequent submissions to academic journals would be considered plagiarism.

The majority of comments about Octopus functionality related to interoperability on the level of publications, technical infrastructure, and peer review.

For publications, participants asked whether preprints such as those published on arXiv (<https://arxiv.org/>) or bioRxiv (<https://www.biorxiv.org/>) could be retroactively imported into Octopus. For librarians, they emphasised the importance of tying Octopus publications into existing tracking systems for publication metrics such as Altmetrics, and functionality to explore how they are cited in other works.

Technical interoperability is important to researchers in several ways. One is a desire for an Octopus application programming interface (API), where researchers can automate publishing to Octopus—or extracting data from Octopus publications—using scripts within their computational workflows. They believe having a programmable interface in parallel to the current web-based forms would ease collaboration between technical and non-technical researchers.

A related feature request is for Octopus to automate publishing through external triggers. Specifically, they cited the integration between Zotero (<https://www.zotero.org/>) and Figshare (<https://www.figshare.com/>) with GitHub (<https://www.github.com/>), a popular code hosting and version control platform. While the software development process in a GitHub repository is continuous, a user could "tag" a particular snapshot for release. The associated Zotero (or Figshare) item would be triggered to save a copy of that snapshot with a new digital object identifier (DOI). The bioinformatician from one focus group believed having such a feature for Octopus would allow researchers to try the platform without major changes to their existing computational workflow. Similarly, one librarian described it as "a good kind of easy selling point."

There is also a desire from participants for integrating Octopus into other open research infrastructures. One interviewee in charge of open science at a major non-profit funding body listed the systems they use including Datacite (<https://datacite.org/>), OA Works (<https://oa.works/products/>), OpenAIRE (<https://www.openaire.eu/>), and the Research Activity Identifier (RAID: <https://raid.org/>). In particular, they stressed that their grant management system is struggling to track the research outputs and associated metadata of funded projects. To get an overall sense of a project and its outputs, "you have to do a lot of [manual] curation to link those things."

An initial step, as one librarian suggested, is to embed more structured metadata for Octopus publications, namely the Contributor Roles Taxonomy for describing author roles (CRediT: <https://credit.niso.org/>). A further step would be integration with existing research discovery systems, such as Europe PMC (<https://europepmc.org/>). Ultimately, these integrations are viewed as benefiting researchers, to help them ask "how can I collaborate, who can I collaborate with, [and] who's working on this?"

The benefits of interoperability and integration with other systems is not limited to funding or conducting research. For example, if structured metadata about the nature of research labour is included with Octopus publications, then that could be integrated with job search and networking platforms like LinkedIn. For example, a statistician could showcase their skills on a job search website by linking to an Octopus publication that demonstrates them.

Even if Octopus is widely adopted, some are concerned of becoming over-reliant on one provider. One computational scientist observed that the underlying source code for Octopus is open source, and asked if that means individuals and institutions can host their own instances. If these self-hosted instances could then interoperate ("federate"), it will eliminate reliance on one organisation, thereby increasing the resilience of the overall network.

For peer review, participants wondered if Octopus helps organise peer review, because there is currently little incentive for researchers to do so. One focus group member suggested connecting to existing open peer review groups like Peer Community In (<https://peercommunityin.org/>) or the Review Commons (<https://www.reviewcommons.org/>). For one librarian, allowing researchers to publish peer reviews of works outside of Octopus would increase visibility and adoption of the platform, and facilitate the move towards post-publication peer review.

Lastly, one researcher stated that powerful search and discovery features would make Octopus useful for them, this includes checking "whether the question you're asking is already in there [as a research problem]". Without performant search functions, then "if I have to search for all the possible keywords, like sometimes it's really, really hard to find the results you're looking for..."

How is Octopus already useful?

Several participants identified Octopus functionality that already facilitates adoption, from granular recognition of research labour; focus on sharing more of the research process; multi-language support; to enabling meta analyses.

As discussed in our previous report on research culture, traditional peer-reviewed journal publications are the predominant way of sharing research. A widely-shared sentiment is that author lists on such publications do not communicate the diverse contributions to a research project. For one focus group participant, "it's not immediately obvious which [author made] a more valuable contribution to be like, first or second author say, so I like the idea of [...] being able to kind of split up that recognition [on Octopus]." Granular recognition of research labour also has a practical advantage, where: "...it's quite useful from a scientific approach to know who to email, to ask the silly questions, instead of asking the corresponding author who might have just put the whole publication together." Granular recognition is also appreciated by a librarian, who hoped they can one day receive authorship on an Octopus publication, as librarians are historically under-recognised in research outputs.

For a traditional paper-focused publication process, it often forces a researcher to retroactively develop a narrative for their research, and that's after a "several year long research process... [where] you may have changed your mind substantially over what it is that you've been working on since

you started the project." In contrast, participants appreciate the ability to publish more diverse outputs from their work on Octopus, where, instead of the current publish or perish culture, there could be an "attitude shift in scholarly communication mechanisms [that reflects] different elements of research." What Octopus and, to some extent, pre-registration provide is "documenting that process, [providing] much more transparency and accountability and even clarity about your own thinking process and how that's changed over time".

Because of how Octopus publications resemble pre-registration, one librarian believes the platform will be easiest to adopt for researchers in medicine and the life sciences. Octopus could be presented as another way to pre-register research. For the interviewee who works for a research funder, Octopus is also attractive because they want their funded projects to publish results as they are, including "negative results". According to them: "...negative results are not really something people want to, you know, share [in a traditional paper]. But from a funder perspective that is open minded like us [...] we do want that information. We do want the reporting, we don't call it like negative results, we call it just [...] 'results'."

Several participants praised the support for multilingual publications on Octopus. For the mathematician in a focus group, citing very old, non-English papers is common practice: "...a paper from the 1700s is, it can be as relevant as anything else". For the librarian who supports national-level research policy in a South-East Asian country, they described a government initiative to create more academic journals in their native language, and Octopus could be a part of that effort.

Finally, participants perceive Octopus publications to be useful for meta analyses. This could be systematic reviews of clinical guidance for medical research (such as a review of published "Method" publications as the dataset), or as a way to conduct network analyses on researcher roles and how they collaborate.

Barriers to adopting Octopus

Lack of time

While one objective of Octopus is to give granular recognition of labour, there is fear that it will not be accompanied by cultural change where the division of labour is more equitable. For example, when publishing a traditional paper, one researcher's experience was: "it's only me and my colleagues that make everything and detail everything", while other authors did very little. They fear the experience will be the same for Octopus even if the aim is to change authorship politics.

The primary barrier to adoption, however, is widespread perception of a lack of time to learn and use Octopus. As one university librarian described it: "We could certainly suggest [Octopus] to people. What the uptake would be on it, I don't know." Another remarked: "...everybody's trying to do more with less. So yeah, giving people a compelling reason to use their time on this particular platform is going to be the key thing."

This is almost universally supported from focus group feedback where participants—while praising the potential usefulness of Octopus—are hesitant to use it themselves, fearing it will not be worth their time. Many expressed feelings of being overwhelmed with academic work, including anticipating more time pressure later in their careers.

One engineer said: "...my boss is a professor, like he works until midnight [...] so I don't think it will change, it will never change..." When faced with a platform like Octopus, a physical scientist lamented: "...for the people I work with, there's no way they're gonna interact with [Octopus]. It's just not gonna do it... I love the idea, but [...] the workload... It's just like, no, I can't cope."

Another researcher compared Octopus to current preprint servers where there would be "50-60 preprints [relevant to my discipline] per day on arXiv". That is already overwhelming to keep up with, and they fear a similar predicament with Octopus publications. A differentiator between the two is that preprints are close to—and have a clear path towards publishing—a traditional paper, which justifies the time investment.

The lack of time is also accompanied by a perception that it will take substantial effort to learn a new tool such as Octopus. One life scientist described how their lab still worked in a "very analogue way" with physical notebooks, and a general cultural aversion to adopting digital tools.

Using Octopus is neither rewarding nor required

Overwhelmingly, the primary reason behind the perceived lack of time is the absence of career benefits for academic researchers. For Octopus to see higher adoption, "[it] requires an overhaul in the whole system of grant applications, job applications, funding and everything, because if we're devoting time to put it all here rather than writing a Nature paper, say, then that's got to be recognized." One participant observed that: "one thing that is probably similar, no matter what field you come from, is whether or not you're going to get a career benefit from doing the nitty gritty of breaking down all your work." This view is shared by a digital humanities researcher, who believes it is critical for the use of Octopus to have "a career related benefit [...] especially for early career researchers." One despondent librarian who promotes open research practices laments that "...we try and help but sometimes it feels like a sticking plaster rather than [...] actually addressing the underlying issue."

Critically, most participants believed the use of Octopus should be recognised by funding bodies, where "the more kind of funding bodies that recognize [Octopus], then the more that becomes important." Additionally, because UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)—through Research England—is one of the funders of Octopus, a common question during the focus groups was: "What does UKRI want to get out of this?" One researcher asked: "I was just wondering if UKRI has planned anything to incentivize people to use it?" Another was more explicit: "'If [Octopus] is funded by the [UK] funding councils and the funding councils want us to use it, then they have to use this rather than the first author or whatever [paper-based metrics] in their grant sifting processes and things."

In addition, some suggested that requiring the use of Octopus in research publishing—whether by institutions or funders—may engender a gradual cultural change where the use of such platforms

eventually becomes normal and expected. A postdoctoral fellow studying abstract mathematics noted that "one of the things that made people start caring about [open access papers] is the fact that most grant awarding committees [started requiring] open access. And since then, all the mathematicians put everything open access." They stressed that, ideally, there should also be "international buy-in" for these requirements. That said, one librarian warned that if the use of Octopus is only required instead of rewarding (for career advancement), "[researchers] will probably still just see it as a box ticking thing, which is another arduous task that they have to do and may not see any purpose in it..." Similarly, the open science lead at a major medical research funder recalled a strong top-down push for pre-registration for their funded projects. However, "at the end of the day, it kind of fell flat, because the community was not ready, the culture, it just never went anywhere..."

As a compromise measure, one focus group participant noted that "if you want to have a permanent [academic] position, you have to publish in [a] very high impact factor journal. And if Octopus can provide some things, some connection with this kind of journal, maybe not *Nature*, but some well known journal, it can be really a plus." Such a connection could be, for example, an academic journal which uses Octopus as an officially sanctioned repository for supplementary materials that accompany papers. They stressed that "it's not a good idea for science, but [for] now it's the rule of the game."

In addition, both researchers and librarians suggested functionality for tying Octopus publications to existing metrics for research impact. This could be the United Kingdom's Research Excellence Framework (REF) categories, the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), or funder measures of public engagement. For the latter, an engineering researcher believes if Octopus would support interactive elements or videos that are friendly to non-experts, then its publications could be an avenue for public engagement that some funders assess. In any case, one interviewee emphasised that these integrations should consider national-level research assessment key performance indicators (KPIs) to incentivise wider adoption.

Incentives also need to exist for research institutions rather than only individual researchers. One librarian suggested that for universities, "...the people who are in charge of the money are the ones who are not as enlightened. So you have to have a financial or reputational advantage to adopting something and pushing something."

Epistemological diversity

The focus group participants revealed a diversity of ways in which research is conducted. Notably, a humanities researcher stressed that "the humanities often get squeezed out of these [open research] conversations [which] are geared towards what works for the sciences, and so I'm thrilled to be part of the conversation."

However, the publication types of Octopus may not be a good fit, where "the norms of [some] fields don't really support the sort of archiving of data, notes, that kind of thing that you might expect in chemistry or lab based work". This is a view shared by three of the research support staff interviewed, where one said: "...for fields where the workflow is less sort of, you know, idea, data gathering, testing, analysis kind of thing, [Octopus] will be I think more difficult to sell". For some

disciplines, "it's sort of internal thinking and a discussion with colleagues and peers. But kind of the process of turning that thinking into something that is shareable is kind of done in quite informal ways." This form of informal or unstructured intellectual work may, for example, take place during a workshop where "you could obviously just record a workshop and put it online, but [...] where it's so freeform, it feels difficult to imagine an audience for that [...] It feels quite tricky... [to] pull out themes and all this kind of stuff. Yeah, that would be a whole other research project in and of itself."

One librarian has worked extensively with researchers in the humanities. According to them: "[On Octopus], you've got hypothesis or you've got rationale. It's not the way that arts and humanities people think, [which is] much more free flowing." This is confirmed by two focus group participants who are researchers in different fields of the humanities. One is a historian, who noted that—with the possible exception of some sub-fields such as epigraphy, papyrology, archaeology, or the digital humanities—"from the humanities perspective [...Octopus] doesn't really add much value". One reason is because single author monographs are their primary research output, so granular authorship considerations do not apply.

The historian further stated that "the intermediary steps aren't really things that can be identified and analysed in their own right". When asked about what those steps are, they described it as a process where research (primarily reading) is deeply intertwined with writing, and a published monograph is the culmination of that process. This research workflow is confirmed by a librarian, where "[Octopus] is almost like a structure which might seem alien to them because they haven't worked out what they're doing until they've written it all down, which is probably the exact opposite of the physical sciences... [some researchers]'s brains are just a flow of consciousness and they've then got to try and wrestle it into [...] an Octopus, which is a visual image I didn't really need."

Perhaps most critically, a sentiment shared by several participants is the lack of representation in the discourse on open research by social sciences and humanities researchers. One gave an example where, during a meeting about research culture, "I'm shocked by how there are 25 postdocs from the different sciences that I didn't even know existed, and I'm the only person from the humanities, and there's one person from the social sciences." If open research practices are decided democratically, then the "scientists are always going to [dominate]". The participants stressed that the Octopus publication model is based on that of the experimental sciences, and if subsequently pushed onto other researchers, "people will also ignore it and [be] very resentful".

Epistemological diversity and disciplinary differences are not limited to social sciences or humanities research. One bioinformatician said that their research workflow is entirely based on computational notebooks. While they expressed appreciation for how Octopus "focused on the quality of the work rather than necessarily the publishability of the work, which aren't terribly correlated", their open-ended workflow is not a good fit with Octopus because "[it will end] up being sort of confined into a what can we publish [on Octopus...] and so on".

For the researcher in abstract mathematics, "all the information about the proof or whatever would be contained within that one [paper]. And so there kind of really isn't anything extra you need to

understand it or to support it. It's kind of an entirely self-contained thing..." while there is nothing substantial in terms of hypotheses or data collection.

The aerospace engineer in one focus group noted that one barrier to adopting Octopus is shared by other open research platforms, namely that industry partners on their projects tend to require research details to be kept secret. In one case, "90% of the work comes from industry. And then it would be like just [sic] impossible to use [Octopus]."

In any case, one social scientist observed that regardless of discipline, there could be researchers who are not academics. These researchers may not have ORCIDiDs (<https://orcid.org/>), which is required for registering an Octopus account. In research, they believe "recognition of non-academic or civil society [...], or even policymaker type contributions that could happen to shape research work [and] reports and things like that [are important]", and asked "how does that inclusion or exclusion [of eligibility] happen [on Octopus]?" They are concerned that because the technical infrastructure and logical structure of Octopus publications are geared for academic experimental scientists, other researchers will feel excluded.

Peer review

One aspect of disciplinary differences is researchers within them have diverging views on what the most pressing problems are. As reported above, the humanities researchers in the focus groups do not believe the Octopus publication types are epistemologically or methodologically compatible with their work. There is resentment towards open research initiatives because they are often informed only by the concerns of STEM research. For example, the push for open access publishing "came from the sciences", which is often well-funded compared to the humanities and can afford high article processing charges (APCs). In contrast, one historian in a focus group stated that within the humanities, effective peer review is widely considered to be a more urgent issue where "it's always really, really hard to find people that are willing to put effort to referee papers..."

In fact, several other researchers, including those in STEM subjects, shared the concern about peer review, noting "if people that behind Octopus could actually aim to change the way we peer review work, I think it would be great. Because as [the historian have] said, the peer review system is just wrong."

Some observed that having more, smaller pieces of open peer review will reduce the burden on individual reviewers who are currently expected to provide a comprehensive critique. One computational scientist used the analogy of open source software hosted on GitHub, where "on your work, you will get like 100 peer reviews [through discussion thread comments]. And then after hundreds, you know that your work is good because 100 people actually look [sic] at your work and just left a comment".

One suggested that if Octopus peer reviews could be integrated with open peer review communities such as Peer Community In or Review Commons, then it can become part of the wider peer review reform movement. This sentiment was shared between focus groups, where another participant believes "if Octopus could take over and maybe in 10 years time, actually completely revolutionise the way we do peer reviewing [that] would be great".

Notably, the librarian who has worked on national-level research policy recalled an effort to incentivise better peer reviews by funding small payments for reviewers, and by giving them "credits" that count towards research assessment. However, they observed that journals still struggled to find reviewers, perhaps as these rewards are too small to enable behaviour change in a publish-or-perish culture.

Fear of scooping

Several participants were concerned that publishing on Octopus—while showing "that you were the first person to have had this idea"—would expose them to scooping by competing researchers. This could mean that competitors get to publish a paper first, which is what currently counts in research assessments. For example: "...if you're working on a new compound [and something is not quite working], but another chemist might see that and go: 'Oh, actually maybe switching that functional group to another functional group is going to make it work'. So you're sort of helping them get there quicker because you've put your results out there, [then someone else would] go off and publish first [...] in a journal." In addition to papers, for research outputs that could be commercialised, there is also fear among some participants that their work would enable others to profit from it first, including by applying for patents.

On this topic, one researcher observed that one advantage of Registered Reports in the current academic system is that they come with assurance of a published paper, while Octopus does not. They suggest that if Octopus collaborates with journals so its publications can be treated as Registered Reports, it may drive adoption.

Fear of scooping also manifests during the competition for grant funding, where "if you're working on something that's quite sensitive and other people are working on something similar, then you might be a bit more reluctant to have all your thoughts out for the public who can then [...] apply for a grant..."

Network effects

In addition to listing barriers, a few participants suggested possible paths towards Octopus becoming more widely adopted. One interviewee supports the professional development of research staff at their university, and described how staff members would utilise social media platforms such as LinkedIn or Facebook for networking. The popularity of these platforms is partly due to the network effect, where their value proposition is proportional to the number of users. In other words: "And you almost felt left out if you weren't [using it]." This participant suggested that while the number of Octopus users is currently low, they can see early adopters seeding its growth so that eventually the network effect of Octopus would create social motivation for researchers to use it.

The focus group participants had suggestions on who those early adopters could be. For instance, one believed that it would take those in leadership roles, such as principal investigators (PIs), to catalyse behavioural and culture change within their projects and research groups. Though to motivate such researchers, "[it] probably depends on that how much visibility that would imply." This view is shared by a librarian, who noted it would take "champions"—including PIs—to drive

initial adoption. They suggested that PIs who, for example, already publish preprints, could be more amenable to publishing Octopus.

A combination of raising awareness for Octopus among all researchers while working with early adopters in leadership roles, one participant believes "the next generation of researchers or one about five years down the line who grow up with this tool and collaborate internationally, I could see [Octopus] being amazing". It is also important for Octopus to be connected to wider institutional reforms where, according to one librarian, "...in future years, [Octopus] may become more useful as the groundswell of open research and different scientific practices is embedded [in research culture]".

Interpretation

Insights into research culture

This round of interviews provided insights into academic research culture, some of which are comparable to what was learned from our baseline evaluation. For example, there is a desire for more granular recognition of research labour which is perceived to be inadequate in traditional peer-reviewed journals. Study participants appreciated being able to publish elements of research as it is being conducted, and compared publishing on Octopus to pre-registration.

However, many expressed frustration at existing barriers within academic institutions preventing the more open sharing of research processes and products. Several participants are sceptical that they or their colleagues will have time to change established ways of working, especially when doing so may be detrimental to their career prospects. Many of these concerns are due to the strong pressure (perceived to be coming from employers and funders) to publish in high-profile academic journals.

Another commonly-expressed fear is that of scooping. In general, the fear is of direct plagiarism, where others may pass off published work as their own without proper attribution. However, plagiarism is not limited to open research or publications on Octopus, and could still take place even in traditional forms of academic publishing.

Fear of scooping also manifests as concern that if research is published too early, competing researchers would take someone's work and "beat" them to winning grants or publishing a high-profile paper (even if attribution is provided). It perhaps seems remarkable that "helping them get there quicker"—as described by one focus group participant—is a disincentive for sharing research in the current incentive structure, and that there is currently a perceived lack of collaborative approach for the benefit of society and individuals affected by the research.

The current study involved librarians and researchers in the humanities, who were not represented in our baseline evaluation of research culture (Hsing et al. 2023a). They shared a perception that the needs, workflows, and research culture of non-STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) fields of research may not have received adequate consideration in the design of Octopus. They also implied that this bias goes beyond Octopus, and is present in general open research discourse.

Perceptions of Octopus

The interviews and focus groups displayed a variety of perceptions of Octopus, which can inform future development and communications about this platform, and engagement with researchers.

Some participant input also demonstrated possible misconceptions of the key aims of Octopus or its features.

For example, several participants suggested integrating Octopus publications with infrastructures for measuring reach and impact. They range from quantified metrics such as Altmetrics to assessments of public engagement or outreach. However, Octopus publications—as the “version of record” and specifically designed to serve the needs of detailed record as opposed to readability for a general audience—are not meant to serve these goals.

Similarly, a common reaction amongst participants is that Octopus reminds them of GitHub, a popular online platform for publishing and managing software code. While some of the comparisons they drew were accurate, such as forking repositories akin to branching chains of Octopus publications, others were not. Specifically, code repositories on GitHub (or similar platforms) are being continuously developed, and do not act as versions of record as they are on Octopus.

These misconceptions also illustrate how platforms used for open research may serve multiple roles, and that researchers may be confused about the delineation between them. Continuing the GitHub example, users of repositories hosted on this platform can choose to create tagged code snapshots that are archived on Zenodo (<https://www.zenodo.org/>). In this sense, this GitHub user is creating a version of record, similar to functionality provided by Octopus. However, participants in the current study did not show finer-grained understanding of how Octopus seeks to serve some goals (e.g., acting as a version of record) while not others (e.g., providing continuous tracking of research work). This further suggests an opportunity for Octopus to highlight its key differentiators from other popular platforms used for open research.

These misconceptions are also evident from the feedback received regarding Octopus peer reviews. Several researchers compared them to those published by communities such as Peer Community In (PCI). However, while some of these efforts publish the contents of their peer reviews, they are of preprints or traditional journal articles. In contrast, Octopus peer reviews are of other Octopus publications, and themselves are considered to be full publications in their own right.

Interestingly, the comparisons to GitHub and peer review communities converged in one comment, where one researcher noted that open source code published on GitHub would sometimes receive comments in the form of discussion threads. These threads can act as a question-and-answer session with the code maintainer(s), highlighting bugs or suggesting improvements. In other words, they often serve as post-publication peer review of open source code. While an individual discussion might focus on one aspect of the code, popular repositories accumulate a large number of discussions that may—in aggregate—provide a more comprehensive, collective review of that work. It may be possible for Octopus peer reviews to collectively behave in a similar way. One potential challenge is that readers might find it difficult to ascertain how comprehensively a particular Octopus publication has been peer reviewed, especially if they have to read a large number of reviews.

Real World Application

Cultural change can be difficult, even when initiated by a research funder. One interviewee represented a medical research funding body, and as described in our Analysis, their attempt to promote pre-registration to funded projects "fell flat" as it was not an ingrained part of research culture in the discipline they fund.

That said, Octopus represents a potential step change on the path to more open research by providing the needed infrastructure ("make it possible") and user experience ("make it easy") as described by the Center for Open Science (Nosek 2019).

The interviews and focus groups we conducted provide actionable insights for Octopus in terms of how it can be better communicated; technical improvements; user experience updates; and organisational changes.

Communicating Octopus

A frequently asked question during the interviews and focus groups was what differentiates Octopus from other platforms for publishing open research, such as Zenodo or the Open Science Framework (OSF: <https://osf.io/>). As one participant asked: "Why would you choose this over something else?"

Currently, the Octopus homepage presents the platform as the "primary research record where researchers publish their work in full detail". Based on feedback we received, this may be inadequate in expressing key differentiators of Octopus such as its eight publications types; which benefits this structure confers; or the precise meaning of "version of record". Confusion about the latter is evident in the way participants compared Octopus to tools they are familiar with.

For example, several researchers compared Octopus to digital and computational notebooks, or software code repositories hosted on GitHub. While these tools can indeed provide an open research record, the comparisons suggest a misunderstanding of how the version of record that Octopus seeks to create is different.

Similarly, some suggested using Octopus Peer Review publications as reviews of traditional papers, or integrating Octopus with open peer review initiatives. As discussed previously, this feedback implies a misunderstanding of the purposes of Peer Reviews published on Octopus.

With this in mind, communication about Octopus should include not only a description of what it is, but also what it means. A tangible change to the Octopus website could be a bullet point summary of its key features and what they mean for researchers.

It may be a challenge to communicate Octopus differentiators with conciseness and nuance. For instance, while comparisons to managing code on GitHub may be inaccurate, analogies to specific GitHub features may help with understanding Octopus. This includes the concept of "forking" code, which is analogous to the branching chains of interconnected Octopus publications. Or, GitHub workflows allow taking a tagged snapshot of code, and publishing it as the version of

record on Zenodo. That snapshot could alternatively be published to Octopus if interoperability between platforms is achieved.

Some participants appreciated the granular recognition of research labour enabled by Octopus publications. However, they feared the practice of listing powerful researchers as authors—despite negligible contributions—could still occur for Octopus publications. This could be an opportunity for the Octopus team to highlight its publication types, where it would be more difficult to justify the inclusion of those authors on, for example, Methods, Results, or Analysis publications.

Or, Octopus could highlight how its constituent publication types would ease meta analyses, a benefit highlighted by focus group participants. One way to implement a meta analysis would be a single Analysis publication which links to multiple Results publications by other research groups. Another form would be a new chain of research starting with Research Problem that collates and analyses the methodologies (perhaps published as Methods) employed to study a particular topic.

Importantly, communication about Octopus should be sensitive to the diversity of possible users, especially those from non-STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) fields of research or not based in academic institutions. There are existing publications on Octopus representing a slice of this diversity, such as those on archaeology (e.g. Chi 2023), and could be used as examples during outreach. Care should also be taken to not inadvertently use language that is exclusionary of epistemological diversity. For example, as stressed by the historian in one focus group, the presentation of Octopus should not come across as pushing an experimental science-based paradigm onto other research fields.

In any case, continued user feedback and targeted engagement may be needed to further elucidate the precise ways to accurately communicate the usefulness of Octopus while representing diverse fields of research.

Technical changes

Several participants suggested allowing more machine-readable structured metadata to be attached to Octopus publications. This could be United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) or assessment categories in the REF, though the latter could inadvertently create the impression that Octopus is only for research based in the UK.

Metadata could also express finer details about author contributions. Adopting existing standards such as CRediT may be a simple first step for this purpose, but there is substantial overlap between CRediT and the authorship contributions implied by the Octopus publication types. Instead, future work could develop a skills taxonomy that represents the authors who publish on Octopus, and allow tagging publications with them.

One interviewee touted the potential benefits of this metadata for career advancement. For example, a researcher could allow their profile on the professional networking platform LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/>) to extract information about their skills from Octopus publications. This could be recorded in the metadata of an Analysis publication that describes the specific statistical methods or lab techniques this researcher used.

In addition to metadata, there is desire from researchers of computation-intensive fields for programmatic ways to publish with Octopus. Specifically, these researchers often conduct their work with computational notebooks such as Jupyter (<https://jupyter.org>). Rather than manually uploading outputs through the Octopus web interface, an Octopus application programming interface (API) would allow researchers to write code for automating publication of computation outputs from these digital notebooks. In addition to convenience, being able to script interactions with Octopus improves reproducibility and enables interoperability with other platforms.

Interoperability would not only "make it easy" for individual researchers, but also research institutions. As previously described, one interviewee suggested that grant management systems used by funders are inadequate for tracking outputs from their funded research. If those systems could easily interoperate with Octopus, it may also make it easier for these funders to encourage open research among their grantees.

Interoperability can also be between self-hosted instances of Octopus. Here, an instance is defined as hosting the entire Octopus infrastructure—from backend to frontend (with possible cosmetic changes to branding)—on an independent server.

In practice, this could mean universities hosting their own Octopus instances, each holding only the publications from their institution. Interoperability would allow one to use any instance to access and retrieve information from any other instance in the connected network. This typology would not only decentralise storage and maintenance, but also reduce reliance on one provider.

User experience

In contrast with programmatic access to Octopus, several researchers identified friction in the user experience of the Octopus web-based publishing process.

For example, the author approval process was confusing to a librarian who has published on Octopus. Starting with the automated approval email, they struggled to understand whether they are being asked by a co-author to verify their identity; connection with the publication; or approval for it to be published.

Other participants stressed the need for Octopus to be easier to use and less restrictive than systems currently used by academic journals. This includes the ease with which Octopus publications are drafted and submitted, and advanced search functionality that minimises the mental effort and time for a visitor to find relevant publications.

There was insufficient time during the interviews and focus groups to comprehensively elucidate specific pain points, and future work should include wider user testing to inform user experience improvements.

Organisational strategies

Our results suggest that the growth and sustainability of Octopus rely on coordination with other organisations, from research institutions, funding bodies, to traditional academic publishers.

Several participants based in the UK observed that Octopus is funded by UKRI, and asked about what UKRI is doing to incentivise researchers to publish on the platform. For the goals of Octopus to be realised—such as reducing publication bias, publishing diverse outputs, or recognition for different roles—our findings suggest that reforms to assessment by funding bodies are needed to ensure positive career outcomes from conducting open research.

Even though Octopus Peer Reviews are different from open peer reviews of traditional academic articles, there remains the potential to learn from how they are organised. For example, the Journal of Open Source Software (JOSS: <https://joss.theoj.org>) or pyOpenSci (<https://www.pyopensci.org/about-peer-review/index.html>) are academic journals where open peer review occur in discussion threads hosted on GitHub repositories. As mentioned in our Interpretation article, comments in these review threads may come from multiple readers, and might not be individually comprehensive. However, this collective review process could provide a comprehensive review in aggregate. Octopus could learn from this success when designing interventions to encourage the publication of Peer Review items.

Furthermore, coordination with academic journals could take the form of Octopus acting as the designated repository for the "supplementary material" often associated with traditional papers. Octopus can also be treated as a preprint server, where material eventually to be submitted to a journal could be published. This coordination should ensure that submissions to traditional journals should not be treated as plagiarism if their constituent material was previously published on Octopus. Implementing the above could at least partly alleviate the fear of being scooped, as expressed by study participants.

Octopus could also coordinate with open research infrastructure providers such as interoperability (e.g., OpenAIRE) or discovery services (e.g. Europe PMC). Interoperability with these established platforms may further establish the legitimacy of Octopus while increasing its visibility to researchers.

While some focus group participants expressed concern that some researchers, such as those in mathematics or the humanities, may feel resentment towards how Octopus is currently presented, this is also an opportunity for deeper engagement with those groups.

For example, Octopus could identify and engage with a few research groups of researchers working in disciplines currently under-represented on Octopus. The team would work closely with these groups, providing expert guidance throughout the research lifecycle on publishing their work to Octopus. This may result in not just a set of new Octopus publications, but also a complete case study for use in future outreach and ethnographic study to inform further improvements to the platform.

Finally, certain technical requirements for publishing on Octopus may be off-putting. For instance, one focus group participant noted that Octopus requires one to have an ORCID when creating an account, and that organisations listed in a publication appear to require Research Organization Registry IDs (ROR) (<https://ror.org/>) (although in fact this is not actually a requirement). While good practice for open research, the ubiquitousness of these identifiers is uneven across diverse fields of research and institutions. The participant observed that certain non-profit or government research organisations do not have ROR identifiers, and the use of ORCID iDs is lacking in some fields of research. For Octopus, managing this tradeoff between the use of open research technical standards and creating a welcoming experience for diverse researchers may be challenging.

Policy implications

As reported here and in our Analysis, participants highlighted several barriers to open research and publishing on Octopus, from pressure to publish in traditional academic journals to fears of scooping. Some also discussed the role of research policy in shaping these tensions.

For example, one librarian described a government initiative to create new academic journals in the primary language of a South-East Asian country. The literature review in our baseline evaluation of research culture suggests that the dominance of English academic journals creates inequalities in the dissemination of research. The creation of these new journals may alleviate that problem. However, they do not alter the underlying incentive structure where traditional peer-reviewed articles are valued above other outputs. In contrast, Octopus seeks to fundamentally change the research publishing system while providing multilingual support.

Critically, both librarians and researchers noted that Octopus is currently supported by UKRI through Research England. They stressed that this support is inadequate on its own and asked: "What does UKRI want to get out of this?" and "...[has UKRI] planned anything to incentivize people to use it?"

Appendix

Positionality statements

Pen-Yuan Hsing has a PhD in biology, with highly multidisciplinary experience ranging from ecology and conservation, engineering, citizen science, to meta-research on open research best practices. Having developed and published relevant training material, online courses, books, and policy documents on the international level, Pen is a strong advocate for the idea that good research is open research. As someone who belongs to an ethnic minority group during their research career, Pen is particularly sensitive to issues of diversity related to geographical origin and language.

Alex Freeman has a DPhil in biology, which she followed with a career in factual television and the media. She has spent the last 6.5 years working in an interdisciplinary group in academia on evidence communication (funded by the David & Claudia Harding Foundation) and here came up with the concept of Octopus. She is the sole Director of Octopus CIC which is a UK-registered not-for-profit company, from which she derives no salary. She does unpaid work advocating for and developing Octopus in collaboration with Jisc, and is also a strong believer in Open Science practices and research transparency. Octopus is currently funded by Research England, and has previously had awards from Mozilla, the Royal Society and an anonymous philanthropist.

Marcus Munafò has a PhD in health psychology, and has worked across a range of disciplines in the biomedical sciences (public health, primary care, clinical pharmacology, psychiatry, epidemiology). He is a proponent of open research and scholarship, and co-founded the UK Reproducibility Network, which receives funding from several major funders, including a Research England Development Fund award to promote open research practices. He is also co-director of the Tobacco and Alcohol Research Group (TARG), which is based within the School of Psychological Science at the University of Bristol, and a Programme Lead within the MRC Integrative Epidemiology Unit at the University of Bristol.

Jackie Thompson has a PhD in experimental psychology, followed by several years postdoctoral research experience in various sub-disciplines of psychology and meta-research. She has spent several years as an advocate for open research practices within psychology and academia more broadly, including working with the UK Reproducibility Network on several initiatives, mainly due to training researchers in open research practices.

Acknowledgements

This evaluation was supported by [Research England](#) and [Jisc](#), as part of the [Octopus](#) project. The research was carried out within, and with support from, the Tobacco and Alcohol Research Group (TARG) meta-research group within the School of Psychological Science at the University of Bristol, United Kingdom.

We thank the 11 researchers for giving their valuable time for the focus groups, including those who were willing to be named here (in alphabetical order of first name): Alessandro Pontillo, Maya Anderson-González, and Richard Acton.

We are also grateful to the five interviewees, all of who were willing to be acknowledged here (in alphabetical order of first name): Chris Erdmann, Kirsty Merrett, Lydia Klimecki, Madiareni Sulaiman, Zosia Beckles.

References

- Chi, A. (2023) A Framework for the Study of “Mercury Jars” and Other Stoneware - Research Problem. *Octopus*. <https://doi.org/10.57874/assa-nb08>
- Hsing, P.-Y., Tukanova, M., Freeman, A., Munafo, M., & Thompson, J. (2023a). A snapshot of the academic research culture in 2023 and how it might be improved. *Octopus*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8165703>
- Hsing, P.-Y., Freeman, A., Thompson, J. (2023b) Survey to help identify whether Octopus might help researchers produce high quality, open research - Method. *Octopus*. <https://doi.org/10.57874/1c7r-nc49>
- Hsing, P.-Y., Freeman, A., Thompson, J. (2023c) Qualitative interviews to identify whether Octopus might help researchers produce high quality, open research - Method. *Octopus*. <https://doi.org/10.57874/tx7n-ff73>
- Nosek, B. (2019) Strategy for Culture Change. *Center for Open Science*. <https://www.cos.io/blog/strategy-for-culture-change>